

F-KANs: Federated Kolmogorov-Arnold Networks

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Abstract—In this paper, we present an innovative federated learning (FL) approach that utilizes Kolmogorov-Arnold Networks (KANs) for classification tasks. By utilizing the adaptive activation capabilities of KANs in a federated framework, we aim to improve classification capabilities while preserving privacy. The study evaluates the performance of federated KANs (F-KANs) compared to traditional federated Multi-Layer Perceptrons (F-MLPs) on classification task. The results show that the F-KANs model significantly outperforms the F-MLP model in terms of accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score and stability, and achieves better performance, paving the way for more efficient and privacy-preserving predictive analytics.

Index Terms—federated learning, Kolmogorov-Arnold Networks, classification, artificial intelligence

I. INTRODUCTION

Classification tasks are of central importance for various applications such as medical diagnosis, spam detection and image recognition [1]. Traditional methods often rely on large centralized datasets, which raises concerns about data privacy and potential data breaches. Machine learning models, particularly deep learning architectures, have shown promise when it comes to capturing complicated patterns for classification [2]. However, these models often require large amounts of data, which poses privacy and data security issues. Federated Learning (FL) provides a solution by enabling collaborative model training across multiple decentralized devices while keeping the data localized [3]. On the other hand, research on the application of KANs in wireless networks is a relatively new and specialized area within the broader context of neural networks and their applications to wireless communications. The paper [11] presents a novel method to improve intrusion detection in Internet of Things (IoT) environments where the proposed approach leverages KANs in combination with ensemble learning techniques to enhance the accuracy and robustness of intrusion detection systems (IDS). The paper [12] introduces an explainable unsupervised anomaly detection framework specifically designed for the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) and uses Convolutional and CBAM-enhanced Temporal Attention KAN (CCTAK). However, the application of federated learning in this context has not yet been presented.

In this study, federated KANs (F-KANs) are presented that combine the strengths of FL with the innovative architecture of

KANs [4] inspired by the Kolmogorov-Arnold representation theorem. In contrast to conventional neural networks, KANs use spline-based univariate functions as learnable activation functions, which improves their adaptability and interpretability. Previous works on KANs have explored the extension of KANs into convolutional architectures [5], graph-structured data [6], time series prediction [7], [8], vision tasks [9], GNN model leveraging KANs [10]. Despite these advances, the application of KANs in federated learning (referred to as F-KANs) has not yet been explored. This paper investigates the application of F-KANs to classification tasks and compares their performance with traditional F-MLPs on a diverse classification dataset. Table I contains the notation table used throughout the paper.

TABLE I: Notations used throughout the paper.

Notation	Description
(X, y)	Dataset features and labels
(X_{train}, y_{train})	Training set features and labels
(X_{test}, y_{test})	Testing set features and labels
\mathcal{D}_{train}	Training TensorDataset
\mathcal{D}_{test}	Testing TensorDataset
N	Number of clients
$\{\mathcal{D}_{train}^i\}_{i=1}^N$	Partitioned training datasets for each client
θ_G	Global model parameters
$\{\theta_i\}_{i=1}^N$	Client model parameters
\mathcal{L}	Loss
\mathcal{A}	Accuracy
R	Number of federated learning rounds
S	Number of training steps per round
Φ	Matrix comprising univariate functions in a KAN layer
$\varphi_{i,j}(\cdot)$	Univariate function from input i to output j in a KAN layer
n_k	Number of data samples in client k
m_r	Total number of data samples for round r

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT AND FEDERATED KOLMOGOROV-ARNOLD NETWORKS BACKGROUND

We address the problem of classification in a federated learning environment. Specifically, we are concerned with classifying data points based on features that are distributed across multiple clients. Each data point at time t is represented by a feature vector \mathbf{x}_t and the goal is to predict the class label y_t . The Kolmogorov-Arnold representation theorem underlies the architecture of KANs and allows any multivariate continuous function to be represented as a composition of simple univariate functions. This study extends this concept to a federated environment where each client trains a F-KAN model locally and a central server aggregates the model updates without accessing the raw data, thus preserving privacy.

Federated Kolmogorov-Arnold Networks (F-KANs) extend the concept of KANs by leveraging the Kolmogorov-Arnold

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representation theorem within a FL framework. The theorem states that any multivariate continuous function can be represented by a finite composition of univariate functions. This allows F-KANs to replace traditional linear weights with spline-based univariate functions along the edges of the network, structured as learnable activation functions, while enabling decentralized training across multiple clients. An F-KAN layer is defined by a matrix Φ comprising univariate functions $\varphi_{i,j}(\cdot)$ with $i = 1, \dots, N_{\text{in}}$ and $j = 1, \dots, N_{\text{out}}$, where N_{in} and N_{out} denote the number of inputs and outputs, respectively. These univariate functions are usually approximated with B-splines, which enable smooth and continuous interpolation between control points. The architecture of F-KANs includes multiple layers, with each layer transforming the input through spline-based activation functions. This design improves the model's ability to learn complex patterns than traditional federated MLPs (F-MLPs). In a federated environment, multiple clients independently train local F-KAN models on their respective datasets. The local models regularly exchange their updates with a central server, which performs federated averaging to update the global model. This iterative process continues until the global model converges. This ensures better performance while maintaining data privacy between clients.

III. PROPOSED METHOD

Fig. 1 illustrates the functionality of F-KANs and the interaction between the global model and several clients. At the beginning, the global KAN model is initialized. Each client has its share of the local data. Each client trains a local KAN model using its local data set and sends the model updates back to the central server. The central server performs federated averaging to aggregate the local updates and update the global model. This process is repeated for a certain number of rounds, continuously improving the global model. Finally, the updated global model is evaluated on a test dataset. Fig. 1 shows these steps with nodes representing the main operations and arrows indicating the flow and iteration of the federated learning process. In summary, F-KANs uses decentralized data to jointly train a robust global model without sharing local data directly. Algorithm 1 provides the pseudo-code of the F-KAN algorithm. The main algorithm comprises loading and preprocessing data, partitioning data for clients, defining and initializing the F-KAN classifier and calling the federated learning KAN process. The individual function definitions in this algorithm are as follows: *create_dataset* converts a data loader into tensors for training input and labels. *fed_avg* averages the parameters of client models to update the global model. *compute_metrics* computes the average loss, accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score over a dataset. *federated_learning_KAN* manages the federated learning process by iterating over rounds, training client models, updating the global model, and computing metrics.

Algorithm 1 Federated Learning with KAN

Inputs and Outputs

- 1: **Input:** Dataset (X, y) , number of clients N , number of rounds R , steps per round S , KAN model architecture
- 2: **Output:** Trained global model θ_G , training and testing losses $\mathcal{L}_{\text{train}}, \mathcal{L}_{\text{test}}$, training and testing accuracies $\mathcal{A}_{\text{train}}, \mathcal{A}_{\text{test}}$, training and testing precision $\mathcal{P}_{\text{train}}, \mathcal{P}_{\text{test}}$, training and testing recall $\mathcal{R}_{\text{train}}, \mathcal{R}_{\text{test}}$, training and testing F1-scores $\mathcal{F}_{\text{train}}, \mathcal{F}_{\text{test}}$

Function Definitions

- 3: **function** *create_dataset*(data_loader):
- 4: Concatenate batches from data_loader into tensors \mathbf{X}, \mathbf{y}
- 5: **return** {train_input: \mathbf{X} , train_label: \mathbf{y} }
- 6: **function** *fed_avg*($\theta_G, \{\theta_i\}, \{n_i\}$):
- 7: Initialize $\theta_G \leftarrow 0$
- 8: $m_r \leftarrow \sum_{k \in \{1, \dots, N\}} n_k$
- 9: **for each** θ_i **in** client models:
- 10: **for each** parameter θ_G^j **in** θ_G :
- 11: $\theta_G^j \leftarrow \theta_G^j + \frac{n_i}{m_r} \theta_i^j$
- 12: **return** θ_G
- 13: **function** *compute_metrics*(θ, \mathcal{D}):
- 14: Compute $\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{P}, \mathcal{R}$, and \mathcal{F} over \mathcal{D}
- 15: **return** $\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{P}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{F}$
- 16: **function** *federated_learning_KAN*($\theta_G, \{\mathcal{D}^i\}, \mathcal{D}_{\text{test}}, R, S$):
- 17: Store training and testing metrics: $\mathcal{L}_{\text{train}}, \mathcal{A}_{\text{train}}, \mathcal{P}_{\text{train}}, \mathcal{R}_{\text{train}}, \mathcal{F}_{\text{train}}, \mathcal{L}_{\text{test}}, \mathcal{A}_{\text{test}}, \mathcal{P}_{\text{test}}, \mathcal{R}_{\text{test}}, \mathcal{F}_{\text{test}}$
- 18: **for** $r = 1$ **to** R :
- 19: Create client models $\{\theta_i\}$ from θ_G
- 20: **for** $i = 1$ **to** N :
- 21: $\mathcal{D}_i \leftarrow \text{create_dataset}(\mathcal{D}^i)$
- 22: Train θ_i on \mathcal{D}_i for S steps
- 23: $\theta_G \leftarrow \text{fed_avg}(\theta_G, \{\theta_i\}, \{n_i\})$
- 24: $\mathcal{L}_{\text{train}}[r], \mathcal{A}_{\text{train}}[r], \mathcal{P}_{\text{train}}[r], \mathcal{R}_{\text{train}}[r], \mathcal{F}_{\text{train}}[r] \leftarrow \text{compute_metrics}(\theta_G, \mathcal{D}_{\text{train}})$
- 25: $\mathcal{L}_{\text{test}}[r], \mathcal{A}_{\text{test}}[r], \mathcal{P}_{\text{test}}[r], \mathcal{R}_{\text{test}}[r], \mathcal{F}_{\text{test}}[r] \leftarrow \text{compute_metrics}(\theta_G, \mathcal{D}_{\text{test}})$
- 26: **return** $\theta_G, \mathcal{L}_{\text{train}}, \mathcal{A}_{\text{train}}, \mathcal{P}_{\text{train}}, \mathcal{R}_{\text{train}}, \mathcal{F}_{\text{train}}, \mathcal{L}_{\text{test}}, \mathcal{A}_{\text{test}}, \mathcal{P}_{\text{test}}, \mathcal{R}_{\text{test}}, \mathcal{F}_{\text{test}}$

Main Algorithm

- 27: Split into training $(X_{\text{train}}, y_{\text{train}})$ and testing $(X_{\text{test}}, y_{\text{test}})$ sets
- 28: Partition $\mathcal{D}_{\text{train}}$ into N clients: $\{\mathcal{D}_{\text{train}}^i\}$
- 29: Define KAN Classifier
- 30: Initialize global model θ_G
- 31: $\theta_G, \mathcal{L}_{\text{train}}, \mathcal{A}_{\text{train}}, \mathcal{P}_{\text{train}}, \mathcal{R}_{\text{train}}, \mathcal{F}_{\text{train}}, \mathcal{L}_{\text{test}}, \mathcal{A}_{\text{test}}, \mathcal{P}_{\text{test}}, \mathcal{R}_{\text{test}}, \mathcal{F}_{\text{test}} \leftarrow \text{federated_learning_KAN}(\theta_G, \{\mathcal{D}^i\}, \mathcal{D}_{\text{test}}, R, S)$

Fig. 1: Federated KAN Methodology

IV. NUMERICAL RESULTS

A. Simulation Setup

The experimental setup comprises a federated learning environment with multiple clients, each of which has a subset of a different classification dataset (iris dataset in our example¹). The dataset contains features and corresponding labels that come from different sources. The clients train their KAN models locally with the Adam optimizer and a cross-entropy loss function. After local training, the model updates are aggregated by a central server using a federated averaging algorithm. The models are evaluated based on their classification accuracy, precision, recall and F1-score. The code of the F-KAN and F-MLP is available in Github². Table II shows the simulation parameters used in our evaluations.

B. Evaluation Results

Training and evaluation were conducted for both the F-KAN and F-MLP models over 20 rounds of FL. In each round, the model is trained on two client datasets and then the performance is evaluated on a test dataset. From the training information in Fig. 2 results in the following comparison between the F-KAN and F-MLP models. Regarding training and test losses, the F-KAN model shows a rapid decrease in training and test losses, reaching values close to zero in the middle of the training rounds. This indicates efficient learning and excellent generalization abilities. The F-MLP model shows a slower and more variable decline in losses

¹Online: <https://archive.ics.uci.edu/dataset/53/iris>, Available: July 2024.

²Online: <https://github.com/ezeydan/F-KANs.git>, Available: July 2024.

TABLE II: Simulation Parameters

Parameter	Value
General Parameters	
Number of clients (N)	2
Number of rounds (R)	20
Training steps per round (S)	20
Batch size	16
Learning rate	0.001
Weight decay	1×10^{-5}
Dropout probability	0.5
F-KAN Parameters	
Width of layers	[4, 20, 20, 20]
Grid size	5
Spline order (k)	3
Seed	0
F-MLP Parameters	
Input size	4
Hidden layer sizes	[20, 20, 20]
Output size	3

compared to F-KAN. Although it improves over time, losses remain higher and fluctuate more.

In terms of accuracy, the F-KAN model achieves 100% accuracy on both the training and test datasets from round 7 onwards, demonstrating its ability to perfectly classify the data after a few rounds. The F-MLP model achieves moderate accuracy improvements and stabilizes at 90% for training accuracy and 80% for test accuracy in the later rounds. However, it does not achieve the same level of perfection as the F-KAN model. In terms of precision, recall and F1 score, these metrics quickly converge to 1.0 as shown in Fig. 3, indicating that the F-KAN model is not only accurate but also consistent in its predictions, capturing all true positives without generating false positives or negatives. These metrics for the F-MLP model also improve, but show greater variability. They do not reach the consistently high values as with F-KAN, which indicates a certain instability in performance. The training times for the F-KAN and F-MLP models are observed to be approximately 313.61 seconds and 2.35 seconds respectively.

To summarize, F-KAN shows superior performance with fast convergence, high accuracy and stable precision, recall and F1 scores. The model learns and generalizes effectively across the training and test datasets and achieves perfect scores from round 7 onwards. The F-MLP model, on the other hand, shows improvement but more variability and instability in the performance metrics. While the F-MLP model achieves reasonable accuracy, it does not match the consistency and robustness of the F-KAN model.

C. Key Observations

The rapid convergence and stable performance metrics of the F-KAN model indicate a highly efficient learning process. The spline-based univariate features enable F-KAN to capture complex patterns quickly and accurately, resulting in stable and high performance with fewer training rounds. Although the F-MLP model improves over time, it shows greater variability in performance. This could be due to its reliance on traditional linear weights and activation functions, which may not capture the complexity of the data as well as F-KAN's spline-based approach. The ability of the F-KAN model to achieve and maintain high accuracy precision,

(a)

(b)

Fig. 2: Comparisons of federated learning with F-KAN model and F-MLP model over rounds (a) Cross-Entropy loss. (b) Accuracy

recall, and F1 score on both the training and test datasets in relatively early rounds indicates excellent generalization. This is crucial for applications where consistent and reliable performance on unseen data is critical, such as medical diagnosis or autonomous driving. The F-MLP model shows adequate but less consistent generalization capabilities. Its fluctuating performance metrics suggest that it is more prone to overfitting or underfitting, making it less reliable for applications that require high accuracy and consistency.

The F-KAN model takes approximately 301.19 seconds to train, reflecting the complexity of the model and the computational cost of the spline-based functions. However, these costs are justified by the superior performance and stability achieved. The F-MLP model trains much faster (1.83 seconds), which could be advantageous in scenarios where fast model updates are required, such as in real-time systems. However, the trade-off is lower and more variable performance. The high accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 scores make the F-

KAN ideal for applications where errors can have significant consequences, e.g. in critical infrastructure monitoring. F-KAN's ability to capture complex patterns with fewer parameters makes it suitable for tasks involving complicated data relationships, such as image and speech recognition. In addition, the shorter training time makes F-MLP suitable for applications where models need to be updated quickly and frequently, such as recommendation systems or real-time analysis. F-MLPs may be preferred in scenarios where computing resources are limited and a slight compromise in performance in favour of faster processing times is acceptable.

V. F-KANS FOR WIRELESS CASE STUDIES

The proposed F-KANs can be an example of a distributed AI approach that meets the need for decentralized, adaptive intelligence in native networks. This approach can provide several advantages for distributed AI in wireless networks:

- In contrast to traditional neural networks, which are based on fixed activation functions, F-KANs use spline-based univariate functions as learnable activation functions, which allow for better adaptability and interpretability. Thanks to this adaptability, F-KANs can learn complex patterns in data more effectively, which is particularly important for the diverse and dynamic conditions in wireless networks.
- The federated architecture of F-KANs enables decentralized model training across multiple clients without the need to transfer raw data, thereby preserving user privacy. This is achieved by performing local computations on each device and aggregating model updates on a central server, which then updates the global model. Such a system meets the privacy and security requirements of modern wireless networks.
- F-KANs have shown superior performance on classification tasks compared to traditional federated models such as F-MLPs. The use of univariate features enables fast convergence, high accuracy and stable performance metrics such as precision, recall and F1-score. These features are crucial for applications in wireless/native networks that require reliable and timely predictions since they have already AI deeply embedded into their core functionalities and operations.

A. Challenges and Open Research Areas

While distributed AI frameworks like F-KANs offer promising solutions for native networks, several challenges and research opportunities exist:

- Despite the advantages of federated learning, the exchange of model updates between clients and the central server can introduce significant communication overhead especially for bigger models. For F-KANs, optimizing the frequency and size of model updates is going to be crucial to maintain a balance between performance and bandwidth consumption. Techniques such as model compression, update sparsification, and adaptive communication protocols are active areas of research that can be used to improve the efficiency of F-KAN deployment.

Fig. 3: Comparisons of federated learning with F-KAN model and F-MLP model over rounds (a) Precision. (b) Recall. (c) F1-Score

- F-KAN agents in native networks need to communicate effectively across different network layers and paradigms. Optimizing these communication protocols to support efficient and low-latency information exchange is crucial, especially in scenarios requiring rapid decision-making and response, such as autonomous vehicles, drone networks, and smart grid applications.
- The spline-based activation functions in F-KANs are highly flexible, allowing for improved learning. However, the computational complexity of F-KAN models can pose challenges in environments with limited computational and energy resources, such as edge devices and sensor networks. Future research needs to balance model complexity and resource constraints by designing lightweight, efficient AI models that can be deployed across diverse network nodes.
- Native networks are dynamic by nature, with fluctuating traffic loads, device availability and possible failures. The decentralized nature of F-KANs makes them well suited for environments with dynamic connectivity, such as mobile networks or sensor arrays. However, fluctuating network conditions, device availability and data heterogeneity can impact the convergence and performance of the model. F-KAN models must withstand these dynamics and ensure reliable performance even when parts of the network are disrupted. This requires the development of F-KANs with adaptive training strategies and fault-tolerant algorithms capable of handling non-IID (Independent and Identically Distributed) data distributions and network partitions to ensure consistent performance in highly variable network environments.
- While F-KANs offer inherent privacy benefits due to their federated learning structure, the decentralized nature of these networks can introduce vulnerabilities such as model inversion attacks or poisoning attacks. Exploring secure aggregation techniques, differential privacy mechanisms and robust model verification for F-KANs can further strengthen their resilience against adversarial threats.

B. Future Directions for F-KANs in Native Networks

To fully realize the potential of distributed AI in native networks, future research needs to address the above chal-

lenges while exploring new use cases and applications. Some important directions are:

- A promising area of future research is the development of dynamic update strategies for F-KANs that adjust communication frequency and model aggregation based on network conditions. This would improve the efficiency of training in environments with intermittent connectivity or varying bandwidth availability and ensure optimal utilisation of resources while maintaining high performance.
- The use of multi-agent reinforcement learning within the F-KAN framework can improve the decision-making processes of distributed agents in the network. By enabling F-KAN models to learn optimal strategies for managing network resources, balancing traffic load, and adapting to environmental changes, MARL has the potential to improve both the efficiency and intelligence of the network as a whole.
- The modular nature of F-KANs allows for potential hybridization with other AI architectures tailored to specific applications within native networks. For example, combining F-KANs with convolutional neural networks (CNNs) for image-based network tasks or with graph neural networks (GNNs) for topology-aware resource management can lead to specialized models that are both efficient and effective.
- F-KAN research can be accelerated by establishing open source platforms for sharing model architectures, source code and standardized datasets. Such collaboration would support reproducibility, enable benchmarking across different wireless network scenarios, and foster the development of robust and adaptable distributed AI frameworks.

Finally, Table III provides a comparison of F-KAN and F-MLP for use cases in network resource management, edge computing/IoT, network security and privacy, and autonomous network control, highlighting their characteristics, advantages and disadvantages in B5G/6G cellular networks.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

This paper shows the effectiveness of federated KANs in classification tasks. F-KANs combine the strengths of federated learning with the innovative architecture of F-KANs

TABLE III: Comparison of F-KAN and F-MLP Across Use Cases and Domains in B5G/6G Wireless Networks

Use Case / Domain	Characteristic	F-KAN Approach	F-MLP Approach	Pros and Cons
Network Resource Management	Scalability	High due to spline-based functions	Moderate, limited by linear activations	F-KAN is better suited for large-scale networks with dynamic resource demands. F-MLP may face scalability bottlenecks.
	Adaptability	Real-time, quick response to network changes	Slower adaptation, fixed activations	F-KAN achieves faster and more precise adaptability, essential for dynamic network slices in 6G. F-MLP slower to adapt.
	Privacy Preservation	High through federated learning, localized model training	Similar, but less optimized for FL	Both approaches ensure privacy, but F-KAN offers better performance under privacy constraints.
Edge Computing/ IoT Networks	Efficiency	High through FL localized model training	Low computational complexity	F-KAN's computational overhead is higher, but improved performance justifies the cost in critical IoT applications. F-MLP is faster, suitable for low-resource nodes.
	Energy Consumption	Energy-efficient model training but requires more computational power	Low energy, less computational demand	F-KAN achieves better accuracy at a slight energy cost. F-MLP is more suitable for energy-constrained environments.
	Generalization	High accuracy and stable metrics	Moderate accuracy and variance	F-KAN excels in handling diverse data from edge devices. F-MLP may struggle with heterogeneous data distributions.
Network Security and Privacy	Attack Resilience	Better resistance to adversarial attacks via complex functions	Moderate resilience	F-KAN's spline functions increase model robustness, enhancing security. F-MLP is more prone to model attacks.
	Privacy Optimization	Strong privacy by local model training with FL	Standard FL, less optimal	F-KAN provides higher performance under privacy constraints; F-MLP is less capable of optimizing privacy-performance trade-offs.
	Complexity	Increased due to complex spline-based activation functions	Simpler linear architecture	F-KAN's complexity can be a drawback for real-time security applications, while F-MLP's simplicity makes it easier to deploy quickly.
Autonomous Network Control	Learning Speed	Fast convergence, early accuracy gains	Slower convergence, longer training times	F-KAN quickly reaches high accuracy, beneficial for autonomous control; F-MLP requires longer training.
	Real-Time Adaptation	High, supports real-time decision-making	Limited due to slower learning	F-KAN's rapid learning supports autonomous decision-making in real-time applications (e.g., UAV control), while F-MLP is less responsive.
	Model Complexity	Moderate-high, spline function usage	Low, linear weight-based	F-KAN's complexity improves decision-making in complex tasks. F-MLP is simpler, more applicable for tasks requiring quick deployment.

to achieve higher accuracy with fewer parameters while preserving data privacy. The results highlight the potential of F-KANs as a powerful tool for classification in decentralized environments. Overall, the F-KAN model proved to be more reliable and effective for the FL task under consideration in comparison to federated F-MLP model, as shown by its consistently high performance across metrics and rounds. On the other hand, the computational costs of spline-based functions must be better optimized. We have also highlighted F-KANs as a wireless case study. Future work will focus on further optimizing the F-KAN architecture and investigating its applicability to other classification tasks in federated environments, e.g. image classification in satellite and edge networks.

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